

The Dark Sides of Modern Science: Publishing and Dissemination (Part II)

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Abstract: This is the third article in our series “The Dark Sides of Modern Science” and is about publishing and dissemination of science (and knowledge in general). The remarks that we stated in the Introduction of the first article of this series (i.e. “Knowledge Production and Authoring”) generally apply to this article and hence we do not need to repeat.

Keywords: Academic publishing, dissemination of knowledge, ethics of science, ethics of publishing, ethics of knowledge dissemination, morality in science, academic misconduct, corruption in science, corruption related to science.

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110. A Brief Overview of Spin: The Twists and Turns of Scientific Writing.
111. Misrepresentation of randomized controlled trials in press releases and news coverage.
112. Scientists should be allowed to check stories on their work before publication.
113. Enough. Science By Press Release Needs to Stop.
114. Academics, not journalists, responsible for hyping press releases.

7 Credibility, Reliability and Trust

Also see “Reproducibility and Replicability” section in the first article of this series (i.e. “Knowledge Production and Authoring”).

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 48. [Why you can't always believe what you read in scientific journals.](#)
 49. [The Validity Of Much Published Scientific Research Is Questionable \(Part 1\).](#)
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 51. [Why we can't trust academic journals to tell the scientific truth.](#)
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53. New Study Shows You Shouldn't Believe Everything You Read - Even In World-Class Journals.
54. Why You Shouldn't Believe Everything You Read in the Newspapers about Medical Studies.
55. New report addresses misinformation about science.
56. Fraud and outside control destroying confidence in research.
57. Is Most Published Research Wrong?.
58. 'The situation has become appalling': fake scientific papers push research credibility to crisis point.
59. Most scientific papers are probably wrong.
60. How Science Fuels a Culture of Misinformation.
61. Believe It Or Not, Most Published Research Findings Are Probably False.
62. Why Most Published Research Findings Are False.
63. What are climate misinformation and disinformation and what is their impact?.
64. Are scientific articles always reliable?.
65. Reliability of neuroscience research questioned.
66. Can we measure trust in scientific publications?.
67. How I lost trust in scientists.
68. Why being open about science can make people trust it less - and what to do about it.
69. Viewpoint: the world must wake up to threat of mistrust in science.
70. Retracted studies may have damaged public trust in science, top researchers fear.
71. Why people are losing trust in scientists.
72. Public trust in scientists and vaccines likely to be damaged by COVID-19.
73. How to Restore Public Trust in Science and Medicine.
74. How I Became Particle Physicists' Enemy #1.
75. The Strange New Politics of Science.
76. Avalanche of papers could erode trust in science.
77. 2020 and 1 million deaths showed us that trust in science is broken. Now we need to fix it.
78. Why we can't trust academic journals to tell the scientific truth.
79. New Study Shows You Shouldn't Believe Everything You Read - Even In World-Class Journals.
80. Why We Can't Trust the Science Journals.
81. Industry influence: can we trust scientific research?.
82. Understanding and Addressing Misinformation About Science.

83. [A Crisis of Credibility in Scientific Publishing.](#)
84. [The tentacles of retracted science reach deep into social media. A simple button could change that.](#)
85. [Science's credibility crisis: why it will get worse before it can get better.](#)
86. [Egotistical researchers fueling a credibility crisis in science.](#)
87. [Science's Credibility Crisis: Publish or Perish Culture.](#)
88. [Ten Meta Science Insights to Deal With the Credibility Crisis in the Social Sciences.](#)
89. [The Credibility Crisis In Scientific Publishing.](#)
90. [Scientific Publications Face Credibility Crisis.](#)
91. [Tackling the 'credibility crisis' in science.](#)
92. [What are climate misinformation and disinformation and how can we tackle them?.](#)
93. [Tackling the 'credibility crisis' in science: New PLOS Biology meta-research section.](#)
94. [Psychology's Ongoing Credibility Crisis.](#)
95. [Facts alone fall short in correcting science misinformation.](#)
96. [Worries mount about misinformation in science.](#)
97. ['An Existential Crisis' for Science: What IPR scholars are doing to solve the replication crisis.](#)
98. [Why Science is Facing a Credibility Crisis.](#)
99. [What can be done to stop misinformation in and about science?.](#)
100. [A Credibility Crisis in Food Science.](#)
101. [How Research Credibility Suffers in a Quantified Society.](#)
102. [Crisis in academia: 'I love research, but I don't see any security or stability in it'.](#)
103. [Responding to Science Disinformation.](#)
104. [Corruption, Falsity, and Fraud: The Epistemological Crisis of Professional Academic Research.](#)
105. [Why is trust in scientific research at an all time low?.](#)
106. [The Problem of Scientific Misinformation.](#)
107. [Scientific publishing needs urgent reform to retain trust in research process.](#)
108. [Public trust in science has been eroded, from Covid-19 to climate.](#)
109. [The west's crisis of confidence in science.](#)
110. [AI used to target kids with disinformation.](#)
111. [Major declines in the public's confidence in science in the wake of the pandemic.](#)
112. [Why do so many Americans distrust science?.](#)
113. [Trust in scientists is eroding and we need to get it back. Transparency is more important than ever.](#)

114. Addressing Science-Related Misinformation and Disinformation.
115. Will public trust in science survive the pandemic?.
116. Thumb on the Scale: Public trust in science is eroding, thanks to the scientific establishment's recent forays into partisan politics.
117. Widespread distrust in science: Is the way we communicate to blame?.
118. AAAS Voices: Countering Science Misinformation.
119. Erosion of trust in science.
120. Public trust in science and scientists is declining, new survey from Pew Research Center finds.
121. Why We Don't Trust Science Anymore.
122. One-quarter of Americans have little to no confidence in scientists to act in public's best interests, per report.
123. How universities themselves contribute to the spread of misinformation.
124. Scientific journals have a credibility problem. Here's how to fix it.
125. Assessing the Reliability of Published Systematic Literature Reviews.
126. Secondary school students know how to spot scientific fake news.
127. 6 tips to help you detect fake science news.
128. Fake News in Science.
129. Fact or Fake? Tackling Science Disinformation.
130. Science Education in an Age of Misinformation.
131. Fake news invades science and science journalism as well as politics.
132. Understanding and Addressing Misinformation About Science.
133. Science Misinformation, Its Origins and Impacts, and Mitigation Strategies Examined in New Report; Multisector Action Needed to Increase Visibility of, Access to High-Quality Science Information.
134. Address science misinformation not by repeating the facts, but by building conversation and community.
135. Understanding the Spread of Science Misinformation.
136. Science Misinformation.
137. Fighting Science Misinformation.
138. Misinformation, disinformation and bad science.
139. Systemic solutions urged to counter spread of science misinformation in new report co-authored by Northeastern professor.
140. Our students learn science in school, but are we teaching them how to identify scientific misinformation?.

141. [Can We Trust Social Science Yet?](#).
142. [Stating The Facts: The Rise of Misinformation and Distrust in Science.](#)
143. [Health and science misinformation.](#)
144. [Is There a Solution to Low Quality Research in Science?.](#)
145. [Disinformation and Science: A survey of the gullibility of students with regard to false scientific news.](#)
146. [A Closer Look to the Problem of Scientific Misinformation.](#)

8 Quality and Value of Published Science

Also see “Paper Mills” and “Quality of Academic Writing and Gobbledegook” sections in the first paper of this series and “Gibberish Papers” section in the second paper of this series.

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32. C. O'Grady. Low-quality papers are surging by exploiting public data sets and AI, 2025. DOI: [10.1126/science.zgawnij](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.zgawnij)
33. R. Hill; C. Stein. Race to the Bottom: Competition and Quality in Science, 2025. DOI: [10.1093/qje/qjaf010](https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjaf010)
34. Quality of scientific papers questioned as academics 'overwhelmed' by the millions published.
35. Measures of success: what's the real value of published research?.
36. The world of Poor Things at MDPI journals.
37. Are there actually a lot of academic papers that don't really advance science, or is that a misconception?.
38. Why are many obviously pointless papers published, or worse studied?.
39. Why Academics Are Writing Junk That Nobody Reads.
40. Am I the only who notice a great decline in the quality of published articles nowadays?.
41. Pressure From the Top.
42. Why Garbage Science Gets Published.
43. Is There a Solution to Low Quality Research in Science?.
44. AI Tools May Be Weakening the Quality of Published Research.
45. Quality, trust & peer review: researchers' perspectives 10 years on .
46. We Must Stop the Avalanche of Low-Quality Research.
47. AI tools may be weakening the quality of published research, study warns.
48. Can We Trust Social Science Yet?.
49. Scientific publishing needs urgent reform to retain trust in research process.
50. The pseudo side of science publications: The rise and growth of 'junk journals'.
51. Can you give some examples of "scientific" papers that have been published in reputable journals, but which are considered to be of poor quality?.
52. Early COVID-19 research is riddled with poor methods and low-quality results - a problem for science the pandemic worsened but didn't create.

53. Publish-or-perish: Peer review and the corruption of science.
54. Why bad research is worse than no research.
55. Increase in poor-quality research papers due to the use of AI threatens the scientific field, reveals new study.
56. Publish-or-perish and the quality of science.
57. Low-quality systematic reviews and meta-analyses (misleading evidence!).
58. Richard Smith: Medical research-still a scandal.
59. Any journal editors experiencing a glut of poor quality articles from certain regions of the world?.
60. The Problems With Science Journals Trying to Be Gatekeepers - and Some Solutions.
61. The scientific world does not need more bad quality papers.
62. Fraudulent Scientific Papers Are Rapidly Increasing, Study Finds.
63. REF pushes academics to churn out lower quality research, new study shows.
64. Why Is So Much Published Research So Bad?.
65. Is the quality of academic journals decreasing?.
66. Research Has a "Trash Island." Some Are Trying to Clean it Up.
67. Do you think most academic articles are garbage? If so, why?.
68. Why are there so many studies published out there that turn out to be garbage or misleading?.
69. An Open Access Trash Heap.
70. Garbage in, Garbage Out? How to Avoid Citing from Questionable Sources in Systematic Literature Reviews.
71. Academics Write Rubbish Nobody Reads.
72. For-Profit Academic Publishers Love LLM Garbage.
73. Scientists publish too many useless papers: a global problem.

9 Artificial Intelligence

Also see “Role of Artificial Intelligence in Knowledge Production” section in the first paper of this series. We should also note that some of the items in this section may not belong to “Publishing and Dissemination” but they were included here for common benefit and desire to reduce the number of sections with similar contents and objectives (as well as because of their connection and relevance to “Publishing and Dissemination”).

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118. Why I'm currently declining some unpaid peer-review requests.
119. End the unchecked growth of publishing fees and the overreliance on unpaid peer review.
120. Hidden Cost of Science: The Unpaid Reviewers.
121. Making "Pay Peer Reviewers" More Than a Slogan.
122. Doing peer review for no money: a noble tradition or 'conspiracy' to enrich journal publishers?.
123. Amid high profits and falling wages, peer reviewers must be paid.
124. Unpaid peer review is worth £1.9bn.
125. For Scholarly Communications, Double-dipping is Double the Fun.
126. Addressing the 'double dipping' charge.
127. On open-access books and "double dipping".
128. Hybrid Journals - Are Publishers Double Dipping?.
129. Double-Dipping in Academic Publishing: The Unsettling Exploitation of Authors and Readers.
130. Elsevier - my part in its downfall.
131. Double-Dipping in Open Access: Academic Publishing's Dirty Secret.
132. The costs of double dipping.
133. Double dipping in hybrid open access - chimera or reality?.
134. In Praise of "Double-Dipping" - Fairness, Affordability, Vitality, and Sustainability.
135. Think academic publishers are greedy? Do your research.
136. 'Too greedy': mass walkout at global science journal over 'unethical' fees.
137. Reforms needed to tackle greedy academic publishers.
138. I did my research. Yes, I think academic publishers are greedy. (With notes on publishers' rhetoric and creationism).
139. Are university/college books so expensive due to the fault of publishers, universities or both?.
140. Mass resignation by top academics over "too greedy" publisher, as Council of the EU calls for open access.
141. SSRN sells out to Elsevier.
142. Publisher greed in the pandemic - the clusterburach #UCMIU.
143. Inside Academia's Broken System: The Lawsuit That Changes Everything.
144. The Impending Demise of Greedy For-Profit Scientific Publishers (Part II).
145. Greedy Publishers III: Oxford University Press.
146. Opinion: Greedy academic journal publishers behind knowledge inequality.
147. Publish Rubbish Or Perish - and Pay Through The Nose.

148. [Academic publishing doesn't add up.](#)
149. [Academic journal's entire board resigns accusing Elsevier of "greed".](#)
150. [Greedy publishers are putting the future of libraries at risk.](#)
151. [The Textbook Industry & Greed: My Story.](#)
152. [The end of greedy publishers is near.](#)
153. [Greed and Buffoonery in Academic Publishing.](#)
154. [Sci-Hub Case: The Court Should Protect Science From Greedy Academic Publishers.](#)
155. [Is Academic Publishing a Greedy Industry?.](#)
156. [The Textbook Industry & Greed: My Story.](#)
157. [How Professors Help Rip Off Students: Textbooks are too expensive.](#)
158. [Greedy Publishers Spur the Open-Source Textbook Movement.](#)
159. [A Brief Introduction to Publishing Monopolisation: The Greed, the Bad & the Ugly.](#)
160. [It's Publishers' Greed, Not E-Books, That's Pinching Authors.](#)
161. [Who will save parents from greed of book publishers?.](#)
162. [The elephant in the room: Profit margins, the exploitation of authors and the demand for more ethical wages.](#)
163. [Exposing the Textbook Industry: How Publishers' Pricing Tactics Drive Up the Cost of College Textbooks.](#)
164. [Free labour and academic publishing: can we 'Just say No'?](#)
165. [Who's Benefiting While We Burn Out? How Academia Became Free Labour for Publishers.](#)
166. [Please stop giving commercial publishers your free labor.](#)
167. [Free Information, Not Free Labor.](#)
168. [It's time to stand up to the academic publishing industry.](#)
169. [University staff urge probe into e-book pricing 'scandal'.](#)
170. [Why are \(some\) academic books so expensive?.](#)
171. [Yelling At Floors: Students Stressing About Textbook Costs.](#)
172. [Why Are College Textbooks So Expensive?.](#)
173. [Why and How to Negotiate with Academic Book Publishers.](#)
174. [Why Are Textbooks So Expensive?.](#)
175. [College Textbook Prices Have Risen 1,041 Percent Since 1977.](#)
176. [Scientific publishing is a rip-off. We fund the research - it should be free.](#)

12 Copyright Issues

1. J. Willinsky. Copyright Contradictions in Scholarly Publishing, 2002. DOI: [10.5210/fm.v7i11.1006](https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v7i11.1006)
2. M.P. Anderson. Plagiarism, Copyright Violation, and Dual Publication: Are you guilty?, 2006. DOI: [10.1111/j.1745-6584.2006.00246.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6584.2006.00246.x)
3. L.J. Murray. Plagiarism and Copyright Infringement: The Costs of Confusion, 2008. DOI: [10.2307/j.ctv65sxxk1.18](https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv65sxxk1.18)
4. T. Ahmad; I. Ghosh. Plagiarism and Copyright Infringement, 2011. DOI: [10.2139/ssrn.1839353](https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1839353)
5. J. Bohannon. Who's downloading pirated papers? Everyone, 2016. DOI: [10.1126/science.352.6285.508](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.352.6285.508)
6. C. Woolston. Paper piracy sparks online debate, 2016. DOI: [10.1038/nature.2016.19841](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2016.19841)
7. D.S. Chawla. Publishers take ResearchGate to court, alleging massive copyright infringement, 2017. DOI: [10.1126/science.aag1560](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag1560)
8. Q. Schiermeier. US court grants Elsevier millions in damages from Sci-Hub, 2017. DOI: [10.1038/nature.2017.22196](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2017.22196)
9. Q. Schiermeier. Pirate paper website Sci-Hub dealt another blow by US courts, 2017. DOI: [10.1038/nature.2017.22971](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2017.22971)
10. L. McKenzie. Sci-Hub's cache of pirated papers is so big, subscription journals are doomed, data analyst suggests, 2017. DOI: [10.1126/science.aan7164](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aan7164)
11. S. Lawson. Access, ethics and piracy, 2017. DOI: [10.1629/uksg.333](https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.333)
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 19. M. Naumov. "Elsevier inc. v. sci-hub": some aspects of copyright infringement in digital space, 2021. DOI: [10.1051/shsconf/202110901027](https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202110901027)
 20. F. Segado-Boj; J. Martin-Quevedo; J.-J. Prieto-Gutierrez. Jumping over the paywall: Strategies and motivations for scholarly piracy and other alternatives, 2022. DOI: [10.1177/02666669221144429](https://doi.org/10.1177/02666669221144429)
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 29. [Copyright infringement vs plagiarism.](#)
 30. [Publishers take legal stand against AI training on copyrighted books.](#)
 31. [Meta allegedly used pirated books to train AI. Australian authors have objected, but US courts may decide if this is 'fair use'.](#)
 32. [The Unbelievable Scale of AI's Pirated-Books Problem.](#)
 33. [AI firm Anthropic agrees to pay authors \\$1.5bn to settle piracy lawsuit.](#)

34. [Meta Secretly Trained Its AI on a Notorious Piracy Database, Newly Unredacted Court Docs Reveal.](#)
35. [Group of high-profile authors sue Microsoft over use of their books in AI training.](#)
36. [Copyright issues and Self-Plagiarism in the PhD Thesis.](#)
37. [Plagiarism vs Copyright Infringement.](#)
38. [The Difference Between Plagiarism and Copyright Infringement.](#)
39. [AI companies accused of ‘largest domestic piracy of IP in our nation’s history’ at congressional hearing led by MAGA Republican.](#)
40. [Understanding the Distinction between Plagiarism and Copyright Infringement.](#)
41. [Generative AI Has a Visual Plagiarism Problem: Experiments with Midjourney and DALL-E 3 show a copyright minefield.](#)
42. [Consequences of Intellectual Property Fraud on Patent and Trademark Rights.](#)
43. [Anthropic Agrees to Pay Authors at Least \\$1.5 Billion in AI Copyright Settlement.](#)
44. [AI startup Anthropic agrees to pay \\$1.5bn to settle book piracy lawsuit.](#)
45. [Anthropic AI Class Action: Important Information for Authors.](#)
46. [Meta’s Massive AI Training Book Heist: What Authors Need to Know.](#)
47. [Apple Sued Over Alleged Use of Pirated Books for AI Training.](#)
48. [Society of Authors condemns ‘appalling’ use of pirated books in AI training.](#)
49. [Search LibGen, the Pirated-Books Database That Meta Used to Train AI.](#)
50. [If you’re going to train AI on our books, at least pay us, authors tell Big Tech.](#)
51. [Concerns over intellectual property in the age of AI.](#)
52. [EU orders AI companies to clean up their act, stop using pirated data.](#)
53. [Anthropic settles with authors in first-of-its-kind AI copyright infringement lawsuit.](#)
54. [Scientist vs. publisher: Sci-Hub reveals flaws in academia.](#)
55. [How the Emerging Market for AI Training Data is Eroding Big Tech’s ‘Fair Use’ Copyright Defense.](#)
56. [Academic Fracking: When Publishers Sell Scholars Work to AI.](#)
57. [Anthropic Pirates SEVEN MILLION Books, Faces HUGE Damages \(Bartz v. Anthropic\).](#)
58. [The SoA’s message to Meta: don’t steal our books.](#)
59. [British authors ‘absolutely sick’ to discover books on ‘shadow library’ allegedly used by Meta to train AI.](#)
60. [Researchers in India worry about access amid Sci-Hub ban.](#)
61. [Research Insights #12: Copyrights and Academia.](#)
62. [AI companies start winning the copyright fight.](#)

63. [AI, Copyright, and the Law: The Ongoing Battle Over Intellectual Property Rights.](#)
64. [Case Tracker: Artificial Intelligence, Copyrights and Class Actions.](#)
65. [Anthropic's AI copyright settlement provides legal lessons.](#)
66. [Does Training an AI Model Using Copyrighted Works Infringe the Owners' Copyright? An Early Decision Says, "Yes."](#)
67. [Canadian Author Sues Four AI Companies for Copyright Infringement.](#)
68. [Generative AI Is a Crisis for Copyright Law.](#)
69. [Fair use or copyright infringement? What academic researchers need to know about ChatGPT prompts.](#)
70. [Whose right is it anyway? Copyright and scholarly publishing.](#)
71. [What the history of copyright in academic publishing tells us about Open Research.](#)
72. [Guest Post - Academics and Copyright Ownership: Ignorant, Confused or Misled?.](#)
73. [Right to Research and Copyright Law: From Photocopying to Shadow Libraries.](#)
74. [Managing Intellectual Property in the Book Publishing Industry: A business-oriented information booklet.](#)
75. [Fair use of images in scholarly publishing.](#)
76. [Publishers settle copyright infringement lawsuit with ResearchGate.](#)
77. [The current system of scholarly publishing is the real infringement of academic freedom.](#)
78. [AI, Academia, and the Collapse of Intellectual Property: A Manifesto for Collective Innovation.](#)
79. [The issue of copyrights and intellectual property in academia.](#)
80. [The Changing World of Intellectual Property in Academic Settings.](#)
81. [Who Owns AI-Generated Content? Navigating Intellectual Property and Copyright Issues in Scholarly Publishing.](#)
82. [Indian court bans Sci-Hub, leaving some researchers worried.](#)
83. [Sci-Hub.](#)
84. [Elsevier vs. Alexandra.](#)
85. [Sci-Hub and Libgen Up against Academic Publishers: A Death Knell for Access to Research? - Part I.](#)
86. [Elsevier threatens others for linking to Sci-Hub but does so itself.](#)
87. [Delhi High Court orders blocking of Sci-Hub and Sci-Net in copyright infringement case.](#)
88. [Court tells internet companies block access to pirate research site Sci-Hub.](#)
89. [All you need to know about the lawsuit against Sci-Hub and LibGen.](#)
90. [War between Copyrights and Academic Research: The Sci-Hub and LibGen case.](#)
91. [Judgment Against Sci-Hub is a Win for Authors and Publishers.](#)

92. [Four Ways of Rationalizing Infringement: or, How to Defend a Pirate.](#)
93. [Delhi HC directs DoT and MeitY to block Sci-hub, Sci-net and affiliate websites in copyright infringement suit; Holds Founder guilty of contempt for violating 2020 undertaking.](#)
94. [Four large US publishers sue 'shadow library' for alleged copyright infringement.](#)
95. [Publishers Association statement on The Atlantic article on LibGen and Meta.](#)
96. [Richard Osman urges writers to 'have a good go' at Meta over breaches of copyright.](#)
97. [Textbook publishers sue 'shadow library' Library Genesis over pirated books.](#)
98. [Understanding LibGen: The Controversial Digital Library.](#)
99. [Has any researcher been sued for using Sci-Hub data in their research?.](#)
100. [Sci-Hub Case: The Court Should Protect Science From Greedy Academic Publishers.](#)
101. [Sci-Hub: Police warn students and universities against using 'the Pirate Bay of science'.](#)
102. [A librarian perspective on Sci-Hub: the true solution to the scholarly communication crisis is in the hands of the academic community, not librarians.](#)
103. [Access to Knowledge or Copyright Violation? The Global Science War Over Sci-Hub and LibGen.](#)
104. [The LibGen data set - what authors can do.](#)
105. [The scientists encouraging online piracy with a secret codeword.](#)
106. [Besides Sci-Hub, does anyone know where else I can get a pirated article?.](#)
107. [The Dark Side of Free Access: How Pirate Websites Threaten the Integrity of Academic Research.](#)
108. [Online Piracy and the Disruption of Scholarly Publishing.](#)
109. [Are Open Access Journals Immune from Piracy?.](#)
110. [Fast Company: "Study: Over 50% of Academics Admit to Pirating Research Papers".](#)
111. [Activists Mobilize to Fight Censorship and Save Open Science.](#)
112. [Strategies to Combat Academic Piracy in Research and Writing.](#)
113. [Academic publishing and piracy: where did it all go wrong?.](#)
114. [How Piracy Became a Cause Celebre in the World of Academics.](#)
115. [What If Academic and Scholarly Publishers Paid Research Authors?.](#)
116. [Paper Pirates: Does Sci-Hub Help or Hurt Research?.](#)
117. [From Book Piracy to Predatory Publishing.](#)
118. [Piracy: A threat to Academicians and Publishers.](#)
119. [Open access and piracy threaten science.](#)
120. [Sci-Hub: research piracy and the public good.](#)
121. [Academic Piracy: Revolution or Robbery?.](#)

122. [Over 90% of chemistry literature freely available at pirate site.](#)
123. [Question on Authors thoughts on pirating books. PLEASE dont share any sites where you can download them, it is against the subs policy.](#)
124. [How to Stop Book Piracy: A Complete Guide for Authors & Publishers.](#)
125. [‘We’re told to be grateful we even have readers’: pirated ebooks threaten the future of book series.](#)
126. [Authors call on Government to tackle online book piracy.](#)
127. [How pirate websites undermine research integrity.](#)
128. [Why book piracy is killing libraries, indie voices, diversity and small presses.](#)
129. [Authors and Book Piracy.](#)
130. [Resolved: book piracy badly hurts at least some authors.](#)
131. [BLOG: How Book Piracy Impacts Authors.](#)
132. [It is not ethical to pirate an author’s work without their permission.](#)
133. [How Internet Pirates Affect Authors and the Publishing Industry.](#)

13 Other Dark Sides

There are many other dark sides and aspects of modern science related to “Publishing and Dissemination”. However, due to the limitations on the size of the current study we outline a sample of these sides and aspects with some examples and prompts that can help the interested readers and researchers to appreciate the significance of these categories and reach the relevant items (papers and online articles) in these categories (as well as encouraging researchers to investigate these aspects). More examples (related to these categories as well as other categories) may also be found in the upcoming Miscellaneous section (see § 14) as well as the previous and forthcoming publications in this series.^[1]

13.1 Spamming in Academic Publishing

A sample of papers and online articles in this category are:

1. M. Kozak; O. Iefremova; J. Hartley. Spamming in scholarly publishing: A case study, 2015. DOI: [10.1002/asi.23521](https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23521)

^[1] We should note that some of the following examples of “Other Dark Sides” (as presented in the following subsections) may also be examples (to some extent) for the upcoming “Virgin or Under-Researched Dark Sides” section (see § 15).

2. A.R. Memon. Predatory Journals Spamming for Publications: What Should Researchers Do?, 2018. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-017-9955-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-017-9955-6)
3. J. Soler; A. Cooper. Unexpected Emails to Submit Your Work: Spam or Legitimate Offers? The Implications for Novice English L2 Writers, 2019. DOI: [10.3390/publications7010007](https://doi.org/10.3390/publications7010007)
4. J.A.T. da Silva; A. Al-Khatib; P. Tsigaris. Spam emails in academia: issues and costs, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-019-03315-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03315-5)
5. J. Sureda-Negre; A. Calvo-Sastre; R. Comas-Forgas. Predatory journals and publishers: Characteristics and impact of academic spam to researchers in educational sciences, 2022. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1450](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1450)
6. M. Dadkhah; A.M. Raja; A.R. Memon; et al. A Toolkit for Detecting Fallacious Calls for Papers from Potential Predatory Journals, 2023. DOI: [10.34172/apb.2023.068](https://doi.org/10.34172/apb.2023.068)
7. J. Soler; Y. Wang. Predatory Publishers' Spam Emails as a Symptom of the Multiple Vulnerabilities in Academia, 2023. DOI: [10.4324/9781003170723-3](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003170723-3)
8. [Science's spam epidemic.](#)
9. [Endless spam since I published a paper a few months ago.](#)
10. [Freeing yourself from unwanted journal and conference email solicitations.](#)
11. [Strange journal invitations popping up in my inbox every day.](#)
12. [Web Spamming by Academic Publishers.](#)
13. [Replying to Academia SPAM.](#)
14. [Democratising publishing or dodgy spammers? What 'inclusive' publishers tell us about the state of academic book publishing.](#)

A sample of prompts (for further research in this category) are:

- Spamming corresponding authors.
- Spamming in academic publishing.
- How to combat spam in scholarly publishing.
- How authors protect themselves from academic spam.
- Spamming from predatory publishers.
- Spamming from legitimate academic publishers.
- Spamming from respected academics and researchers.
- Scholarly spamming as a form of misconduct.
- The cost of spamming in scholarly publishing.
- The bad impact of spamming in scholarly publishing.

- The pandemic of academic spam.

13.2 Selective- and Under-Reporting of Results

A sample of papers and online articles in this category are:

1. I. Chalmers. Underreporting research is scientific misconduct, 1990. [PMID: 2304220](#)
2. K. Lee; P. Bacchetti; I. Sim. Publication of Clinical Trials Supporting Successful New Drug Applications: A Literature Analysis, 2008. [DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.0050191](#)
3. I. Chalmers; K. Dickersin. Biased under-reporting of research reflects biased under-submission more than biased editorial rejection, 2013. [DOI: 10.12688/f1000research.2-1.v1](#)
4. M. Kicinski. How does under-reporting of negative and inconclusive results affect the false-positive rate in meta-analysis? A simulation study, 2014. [DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2014-004831](#)
5. W. Foster; S. Putos. Neglecting the null: the pitfalls of underreporting negative results in preclinical research, 2014. [DOI: 10.18192/uojm.v4i1.1036](#)
6. A. Franco; N. Malhotra; G. Simonovits. Underreporting in Psychology Experiments: Evidence From a Study Registry, 2015. [DOI: 10.1177/1948550615598377](#)
7. K. Neves; O.B. Amaral. Science Forum: Addressing selective reporting of experiments through predefined exclusion criteria, 2020. [DOI: 10.7554/eLife.56626](#)
8. [Non-reporting of negative findings.](#)
9. [Illuminating ‘the ugly side of science’: fresh incentives for reporting negative results.](#)
10. [Why Are Negative Results Still Six Feet Under?.](#)
11. [Dickersin K, Chalmers I \(2010\). Recognising, investigating and dealing with incomplete and biased reporting of clinical research: from Francis Bacon to the World Health Organisation.](#)
12. [Selective Outcome Reporting as a Source of Bias in Reviews of Comparative Effectiveness.](#)
13. [Introduction to research integrity and selective reporting bias.](#)

A sample of prompts (for further research in this category) are:

- Selective/under-reporting of results in scientific research.
- Non-reporting of negative results in academia and research.
- Selective/under-reporting and publication bias.

- Criticism of selective/under-reporting in research and publication.
- Extent/prevalence of selective/under-reporting in scholarly publication.
- Impact of non-reporting of negative results in scientific research.
- The bad consequences of selective/under-reporting results in scientific research.

13.3 PhD and Publishing

A sample of papers and online articles in this category are:

1. N. Yeung. Forcing PhD students to publish is bad for science, 2019. DOI: [10.1038/s41562-019-0685-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-019-0685-4)
2. S. Moradi. Publication should not be a prerequisite to obtaining a PhD, 2019. DOI: [10.1038/s41562-019-0690-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-019-0690-7)
3. Editorial. Look beyond publications in assessment of PhDs, 2019. DOI: [10.1038/s41562-019-0763-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-019-0763-7)
4. A.F. Shamsi; U.V. Osam. Challenges and Support in Article Publication: Perspectives of Non-Native English Speaking Doctoral Students in a "Publish or No Degree" Context, 2022. DOI: [10.1177/21582440221095021](https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221095021)
5. H. Horta; H. Li. Nothing but publishing: the overriding goal of PhD students in mainland China, Hong Kong, and Macau, 2022. DOI: [10.1080/03075079.2022.2131764](https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2022.2131764)
6. W. Quan; F. Shu; M. Yang; V. Lariviere. Publish and flourish: investigating publication requirements for PhD students in China, 2023. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-023-04854-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-023-04854-8)
7. M. Khodakarami; F. MohammadRezaei; A. Sarlak; M. Garg; Z. Rezaee. Free-riding in academic co-authorship: The marginalization of research students, 2025. DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2024.105165](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2024.105165)
8. [When publishing becomes the sole focus of PhD programmes academia suffers.](#)
9. [Is it fair/push/force/ask PhD candidates to publish articles before viva?.](#)
10. [Focus on PhD quality, not publications: We need to encourage scholars to become inquisitive explorers, papers will naturally follow.](#)
11. [Study: PhD Researchers Forced to Grant ‘Guest Authorships’.](#)
12. [The Goal of a PhD Program is Not to Write and Publish Research Papers.](#)
13. [Dizzying publication rates by PhD students?.](#)
14. [the PhD and publication/by publication - a very peculiar practice? part one.](#)
15. [Publication requirements for graduation are a terrible idea.](#)
16. [I’ve left my PhD behind, but I’m being put under pressure to publish.](#)

17. Supervisor publishes PhD students work.

A sample of prompts (for further research in this category) are:

- Forcing PhD students to publish.
- Forcing research students to publish.
- Publishing papers as requirement for completing/obtaining PhD.
- Pressure on PhD students to publish.
- Exploitation of PhD students by their supervisors/faculties/seniors in authorship.
- Exploitation of PhD students by their supervisors/faculties/seniors in publishing.
- Negative impact of forced PhD publishing on students.
- Negative impact of forced PhD publishing on quality of academic publications.
- Forced PhD publishing as a cause of misconduct.
- Forced PhD publishing encourages predatory and questionable publishing practices.

13.4 Oligopoly of Academic Publishers

A sample of papers and online articles in this category are:

1. V. Lariviere; S. Haustein; P. Mongeon. The Oligopoly of Academic Publishers in the Digital Era, 2015. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0127502](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0127502)
2. C. Petrini; E. Alleva. On the oligopoly of academic publishers, 2015. DOI: [10.4415/ANN_15_04_01](https://doi.org/10.4415/ANN_15_04_01)
3. P. Mann. Scholarship in a Globalized World: The Publishing Ecosystem and Alternatives to the Oligopoly, 2022. DOI: [10.46692/9781529216677.014](https://doi.org/10.46692/9781529216677.014)
4. L.-A. Butler; L. Matthias; M.-A. Simard; et al. The oligopoly's shift to open access: How the big five academic publishers profit from article processing charges, 2023. DOI: [10.1162/qss_a_00272](https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00272)
5. F. Shu; V. Lariviere. The oligopoly of open access publishing, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-023-04876-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-023-04876-2)
6. J. Pooley. Large Language Publishing: The Scholarly Publishing Oligopoly's Bet on AI, 2024. DOI: [10.18357/kula.291](https://doi.org/10.18357/kula.291)
7. S. van Bellen; J.P. Alperin; V. Lariviere. Scholarly publishing's hidden diversity: How exclusive databases sustain the oligopoly of academic publishers, 2025. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0327015](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0327015)

8. [Challenging the Academic Publisher Oligopoly: Technological and political changes may liberate scientific research.](#)
9. [Inequities of Article Processing Charges: How the Oligopoly of Academic Publishers Profits from Open Access.](#)
10. [More than half of research published by top five publishers.](#)
11. [Your Unfriendly Neighborhood Oligopoly: On the Exploitive Nature of Modern Scientific Publishing.](#)
12. [How the academic publishing oligopoly skews debates on the cost of publishing.](#)
13. ["Big Five".](#)
14. [These Five Companies Control More Than Half of Academic Publishing.](#)
15. [Ending profiteering from publicly-funded research: Tackling the academic publishing oligopoly.](#)

A sample of prompts (for further research in this category) are:

- [Oligopoly of academic publishers.](#)
- [Dominance of few giant academic publishers.](#)

13.5 Setting Publication Quotas/Targets

A sample of online articles in this category are:

1. R. Aulakh. [Mandatory publication in India: setting quotas for research output could encourage scientific fraud, 2016. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.i5002](#)
2. N. Yeung. [Forcing PhD students to publish is bad for science, 2019. DOI: 10.1038/s41562-019-0685-4](#)
3. J.S. Taylor. [To combat poor quality research, eliminate publication requirements, 2024. DOI: 10.17179/excli2024-7428](#)
4. D. Johann; J. Neufeld; K. Thomas; et al. [The impact of researchers' perceived pressure on their publication strategies, 2024. DOI: 10.1093/reseval/rvae011](#)
5. T.T. Le; T.T. Pham. [Balancing the scale: examining the impact of publication quotas on academic well-being in Vietnamese higher education, 2025. DOI: 10.1080/07294360.2025.2486188](#)
6. [Against Publication: The Case for Academics to Write Less.](#)
7. [Setting targets in academia can be detrimental.](#)
8. [The Cost of Publication Pressure: Examining the Impact on Research Quality in Pak-](#)

istan.

9. [Is it dangerous to set quotas for research output?](#)
10. [Does the pressure to publish a certain number of research papers per year affect the quality of the research being done?](#)
11. [What Is the ‘Publish or Perish’ Culture in Academia?](#)
12. [The F-word, or how to fight fires in the research literature.](#)

A sample of prompts (for further research in this category) are:

- Criticism to setting publication quotas/targets for researchers and academics.
- Setting publication quotas/targets damages the quality of academia and research.
- Setting publication quotas/targets encourages academic misconduct.
- Negative impact of setting publication quotas/targets.
- Danger of setting quotas/targets for research publishing.
- Danger of setting quotas/targets for academic publication.
- Extent/prevalence of setting publication quotas/targets in academia and research.

13.6 Fake Acceptance Letters

A sample of online articles in this category are:

1. [Fraudulent submissions and acceptances.](#)
2. [Fake Acceptance Letters and emails.](#)
3. [Paper Accepted...Unless the Letter Was Forged.](#)
4. [Elsevier: Identifying fake acceptance letters.](#)
5. [Fake Acceptance Letters - The Latest Scholarly Publishing Scam.](#)
6. [Warning: Fake Manuscript Acceptance Letters requesting payment in circulation.](#)
7. [How to avoid fake acceptance scams in publishing.](#)

Also see:

D. Stockemer; T. Reidy. Academic misconduct, fake authorship letters, cyber fraud: Evidence from the International Political Science Review, 2023. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1587](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1587)

A sample of prompts (for further research in this category) are:

- Fake acceptance letters in academic publishing.
- Fraudulent acceptance letters in scholarly publishing.

13.7 Self-Publishing

We should note first that self-publishing has good and bad sides and hence it is not entirely “dark side”. In fact, I include self-publishing here mainly because it reflects the unhealthy situation of modern science and its dark sides noting that self-publishing can partly be regarded as a protest movement against the bad situation of modern science (and its “publishing and dissemination” aspects in particular).

A sample of online articles in this category are:

1. [Scholarly publishing is broken: Is it time to consider guerrilla self-publishing?](#).
2. [Do you self-publish your academic paper?](#).
3. [We need to say yes to academic self-publishing but senior academics must lead the way.](#)
4. [The Opportunities and Pitfalls of Academic Self-Publishing: Reflections Ten Years After my Kickstarter.](#)
5. [Academic self-publishing: a not-so-distant-future.](#)
6. [Self-publish and be Damned: A call for Radical Publishing Alternatives.](#)
7. [The Academic’s Guide to Self-Publishing.](#)
8. [Peer review and academic credibility - barriers to self-publishing.](#)
9. [The Advantages and Disadvantages of Self-Publishing.](#)
10. [How I Do It: Successful Indie Authors Share Their Secrets. This week: Orna Ross.](#)
11. [The Rise of Indie Authors: Pioneering a New Era in Literature.](#)
12. [How Indie Authors Are Redefining Publishing and Building Sustainable Self-Publishing Businesses.](#)
13. [Scams in Self Publishing, What You Need to Know | Self-Publishing News \(Feb. 26, 2024\).](#)
14. [All You Need to Know About Scams as a Self-Publisher.](#)

Also see:

1. S. Carolan; C. Evain. Self-Publishing: Opportunities and Threats in a New Age of Mass Culture, 2013. DOI: [10.1007/s12109-013-9326-3](#)
2. M. Hviid; S. Izquierdo-Sanchez; S. Jacques. From Publishers to Self-Publishing: Disruptive Effects in the Book Industry, 2019. DOI: [10.1080/13571516.2019.1611198](#)

A sample of prompts (for further research in this category) are:

- Self-publishing revolution against exploitation by academic publishers.
- Self-publishing as new model for academic publishing.
- Self-publishing to avoid exploitation by academic publishers.

- Self-publishing reflects the bad situation of peer-reviewing.
- Self-publishing reflects lack of confidence in academic publishers and peer-review process.
- Advantages and disadvantages of self-publishing.
- Pros and cons of self-publishing in academia and research.
- Indie authors motives.
- Indie authors movement.
- Self-publishing as protest against bad situation of scholarly publishing.
- Self-publishing as protest against exploitation in publishing.
- Potential pollution of science by self-publishing.
- Preprinting and self-publishing.
- Print-on-demand and self-publishing.
- Scams of/in self-publishing.

14 Miscellaneous

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89. List of scientific misconduct incidents.
90. Fabricated and plagiarized data plague scientific research - and the impacts are far-reaching and long-lasting.
91. The 14 universities with publication metrics researchers say are too good to be true.
92. Bad Science (Goldacre book).
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15 Virgin or Under-Researched Dark Sides

We think the following dark (or potentially problematic) aspects of modern science related to “Publishing and Dissemination” are not properly and sufficiently investigated (noting that there may be some items related to these aspects in the “Miscellaneous” section and possibly other sections) and hence they require more attention:

1. Journal quotas. The following may be an example:
 - B. Park; E. Sohn; S. Kim. Does the pressure to fill journal quotas bias evaluation?: Evidence from publication delays and rejection rates, 2020.
[DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0236927](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0236927)
2. Paper hijacking. The following may be an example:
 - [Paper hijacking: hijackers are attacking journals for hijacking unpublished papers.](#)
3. The academic qualities and merits of academic publishers and editors.^[2]
4. The undue influence and control of academic publishers on science.^[3]
5. Burden of scholarly publishing on (public and non-public) resources. The following may

^[2] We note in this regard that the bosses and editors of many academic publishers are not top scholars (and may not be scholars) and they are appointed based on questionable or ambiguous criteria).

^[3] This should include things like the indirect influence of academic publishers (through their publishing policies and acceptance/rejection of publications) on things like academic and research funding, academic and research posts and tenure, awards, privileges and prestige, and so on. In fact, their more important influence is on deciding the legitimate/illegitimate science and mainstream/fringe science (noting that the academic qualities and merits of many academic publishers and editors are questionable or humble; moreover their decisions are highly influenced by non-scholarly factors such as commercial and public relation considerations as well as the influence on them by governments, industry, ... etc., which makes the environment of academic publishers and editors full of conflict of interest issues and concerns).

be an example:^[4]

Public funds being swallowed up by scientific journals with dubious articles.

6. Exploitation of general assets and resources.^[5]

We therefore call the researchers in these fields to do more investigations and publications about these aspects.^[6]

^[4]Some labels that may represent and depict this category are: “drainage of public funds by academic publishing”, “waste of public funds by academic publishing”, “waste of valuable academic resources on worthless publications”, “burden of scholarly publishing on science resources”, and so on.

^[5]“Assets and resources” should include general assets and resources in the form of (public and non-public) media and books (as well as documents in general such as pdf files of valuable content, presentations, online articles, videos, etc.), open-access and paywall scholarly products, general and specialized data and information, and so on. The exploitation of these resources is exemplified by the exploitation by the artificial intelligence companies and related scholarly publishing industry (some of which have been highlighted in the current and previous articles of this series). In fact, there are many illegitimate and questionable uses of these assets and resources (noting as well that there are many loopholes in the legal framework that regulates or supposedly-regulates the use of these assets and resources).

^[6]In fact, the above list is a sample noting that there are other aspects that require attention and investigation (especially with the recent developments in academic publishing related, for instance, to artificial intelligence).